

JUNE 20-22, 2019, OPLENAC, TOPOLA, SERBIA

THIRD JOINT MEETING OF NATIONAL PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETIES

In the organisation of a

SLOVAK AND SERBIAN PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETIES

**HEALTH RISK,
NUTRITION AND DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS:
OXIDATIVE STRESS AND POLYPHENOLS IN
THE HEART OF SERBIAN WINERIES**

*OPLENAC
TOPOLA
2019*

FINAL PROGRAM & ABSTRACT BOOK

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SLOVAK PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETY
SERBIAN PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETY

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<http://www.physiology.org.rs/3thNPS/>

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EFFECTS OF VITAMIN D LEVELS ON GLUCOREGULATORY PARAMETERS IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Vitamin D affects the function of pancreatic beta cells, but the effects of vitamin D deficiency on glucoregulatory mechanisms are still inconclusive. The aim of this study was to link vitamin D levels with insulin resistance and insulin secretion parameters. The study included 65 male and female participants, 35 newly-diagnosed, therapy-naïve type 2 diabetics and 30 healthy controls. All participants were tested for fasting glucose, hemoglobin A1c, fasting insulin, vitamin D levels, and the HOMA indexes were calculated using HOMA2 calculator. Fasting glucose levels, insulinemia, hemoglobin A1c levels and HOMA IR were all significantly higher in the diabetic group ($p < 0,001$), while the vitamin D levels and HOMA S index were significantly lower ($p < 0,001$). HOMA-B values did not differ between the two groups ($p = 0,31$). Vitamin D levels moderately correlated with HOMA S and HOMA B indexes ($r = 0,466$, $p < 0,001$; $r = 0,394$, $p < 0,001$, respectively), whereas a negative correlation was found between vitamin D levels and HOMA IR ($r = -0,285$; $p < 0,001$). Multiple regression analysis showed that the vitamin D levels significantly predicted the values of HOMA B index ($p = 0,001$), but it had no predictive value on HOMA IR ($p = 0,26$). In conclusion, the diabetic group showed statistically lower vitamin D values compared with the healthy control group. Connection between vitamin D, glucose levels, hemoglobin A1c and insulin secretion index underline the role of this vitamin in glucoregulation.